

Criminal Exhibit the Feminine Violent Victim within Thai Newspaper

Supaporn Wimonchailerk

Abstract—This research aims to critical analyze the feminine violent within Thai daily newspaper. This study was qualitative base; content analysis from two popular newspapers (Thairath and Dailynews) two qualitative newspapers (Thaipost and Mathichon). Purposive sampling was used to select eleven specialize news reporters to do in-depth interview. The result found that, popular newspapers, Thairath and dailynews have presented feminine violent news in their paper more than Thaipost and Mathichon the qualitative newspaper. Beside, majority of sample present the feminine violent within news under the code of ethic, The National Press Council of Thailand. Interesting, the age of feminine violent victim was the information that has been focused most. The popular newspaper have illustrated crime scene photo on their first-page while qualitative newspaper used only headline to present the same news.

Keywords—Ethic, Feminine, Journalism, Newspaper, Violent Victim.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE presentation of crime news is considered to be one of the functions of the newspaper to meet the needs of readers who seeking information and updating those social movements each day. The Popular newspaper featured a sensational or arousal feeling within the news presented. As well as presenting the crimes to meet the needs of their readers, the news are also represent the public interest, knowledge, and solutions to prevent many crime types. Therefore, crime news is a presentation, which just likes a double-edged sword with both positive and negative effects in the same time. Communicators, therefore, must be aware of the news, they are reporting. Crimes are often involves murder, robbery and kidnapping, forgery and other cruel illegal activities etc. In addition, crimes are also reflects the social conditions that exist in each period of time.

According to the poll made by Suan Dusit Rajabhat University, reveal the violence to life and property reflects within “crime news” occurred in 2009, there is a significant in increasing number with more aggressive violent and more brutal behavior [1]. This survey results are consistent with a report of Thai ladies condition made by the Office of Women and Family Development in 2008. In addition, the Ministry of Social Development and Human Security reports the statistics of women and children experiencing violence, especially the violence against girls and women is likely to increase constantly seen in the evidences of number of recipients of the

One Stop Crisis Centre (OSCC), the agency provides assistance to the abused women and children that illustrates a number of victims have been increased more than doubled from 2004. Average of nineteen abused women or children have been increased to the average of thirty-nine patients in 2006. Crime rates tend to be higher every year as its usually appear more often on the front page of daily newspaper in Thailand, using the inappropriate words and images that verge on the privacy rights of the victim especially with women victims of violence. Illustrating the raped victim or sexual abused victim’s pictures without permission was unfair. The black mark censoring on the victim eyes are useless. Moreover, the descriptions of the crime scenes, the victim’s neighborhoods and their family’s details were stated which is not hard to guess who they are. Another important problem of presenting crime news is the duty of journalists who present the criminal related information under the limitations and difficulties. The Journalists need to work hurriedly to complete with the limit of time. But the mistake occurred, was partly caused by the competition between the news reporter s who wants to get the news before others which lead to careless in checking the accuracy of the information . As the matter of fact, the quickness is not the most important factor. Obtaining accurate information and perspectives is the most important [2].

Nowadays, many events happened each day but there are a few events that have been put forward on the front page of the newspaper as a limitation of spaces in each page of newspaper. Therefore, the event or crimes news need to be considered carefully to be published. The well known newspaper in Thailand is clearly different in the presentation styles. The big news of a newspaper may become a little article in another paper or not at all interested [3]. From the importance of such issues referred above, the researchers are interested in studying the newspaper which report crime news focus the violence against the women and children presented on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand. Total research time is one year duration, from 1st January 2009 to 31st December 2009. The report looks at the news and the practice of journalism in reporting crimes especially ones against women and children victims. To ensure that the professional journalism has paid responsibility to the victims on the news they reported. This research aims to pass on these points of view to those professionals and organizations to consider the newspaper’s content and the impact of adopting these types of crime news presentations. It's also a reminder to be aware of ethical and bring this information to improve the

Supaporn Wimonchailerk. is with the Faculty of Management Sciences, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University , Bangkok, 10300 Thailand (phone: +66896699421; e-mail: Supaporn.wi@ssru.ac.th, Pupa1125@ hotmail.com).

presentation of content as appropriate in order to prevent and resolve social impacts that may occur in the long term.

Objectives of this research are divided into three points. First, reporting the great number of crimes focus the violence against women presented on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand. Second, to study the characteristic of crime news reporting that involves the women victims on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand. Third, to study the practice of journalist on reporting crimes related to women victims of violence on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand.

The research framework was design to study only the crime news reported in Thai language daily large communal newspaper, full size newspaper or a larger Broad Sheets newspaper. (A broad sheet newspaper refers to newspapers with full page by the standards of large sheets (full-size), between 23X25 inches and 23X30 inches that sales available throughout the country every day and have been continuously produced more than 5 years experiences. These sample newspapers are including four brands of the newspaper which are Thairath, Dailynews, Matichon and Thaipost.

This research has led to the development communication concepts with many theories include social responsibility and the ethics and role of journalism to apply as a framework for this research. Researchers have put forward the integration and the established framework of concept to this research as follow.

Fig. 1 Conception framework

From the above conception framework of this research illustrates the presentation of crime news on the first page news paper and the numbers of the women who are the victims of violence. The ethical responsibility that the professional journalist should maintain in delivering any headlines, news, crime news with the women victims of violence are very important to follow.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the Study of “Criminal Exhibit the Feminine Violent Victim within Thai Newspaper” on daily newspapers in Thailand, the researcher has reviewed the concepts, frameworks and theories to adapt use in approaching the studies. All literature reviews can be classified into the following sub-topics.

A. A Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

A concept of responsibility on the media distribution was initiated in 1947 in the United State. A commission on the freedom of the press has prepared a report which clearly shown in the report that, although freedom of the press is to be confirmed the following have identified key practices that the media are responsible for any action [4]. First the reporter must report the incident that happened at around the side of actual scene. And he has to be careful in examine the information without context of event has occurred. Second, the media presented must create a platform for representation and exchange of public opinion. Third, the press has responsibility to represent voice of the society and also presented the goals and values of social advantage.

Karnchana Kaewdevi has present her work in the same direction with McQuail to identified the key characteristics of social responsibility theory of the press into four points. First, the media must conduct a mission to society media should be in public ownership. Second, News media will be truthful, accurate, fair, straightforward and consistent. Third, Media have served as a platform to share the different ideas. Forth, the media should be conducted according to ethical principles and standards of the profession. And in some situations, Society may require intervention to the interests of the media.

In 1948, Harold Lass well (1948) [5], an American political scientist refers to the role of the media in the book called "The Structure and Function of Communication" as three responsible functions. First, work as a surveillance of the environment. Second, work correlate with the different part of society in responding to the environment. The third reason is to be a transmission of social heritage from one generation the next generation. Beside, Schramm and Write (1975) [6] added on the forth of press responsibility, which is the function of entertainment which means to publish convey Thai arts and musical performances into arts of living for the local people.

To summarize, theory of corporate social responsibility, regarding to the social responsibility theory of the press, the professional journalist, therefore shall be concluded in total four important responsible functions and the researcher do believe that, in principle, freedom of the press should be coupled with social responsibility. The presentation of news and facts of the newspaper, must take into account the interests of the reader and the impact may occur to the society should be concerned. The social responsibility theory of the press was used as conceptual framework in controlling the professional press and also to guarantee that the functions of the newspapers will be most effective without any adverse effects to public society.

Researchers put this theories and concepts to create a framework for the research to assess the ethical responsibilities of the press in Thailand, daily news, presentation of the violence against women victim on the first page of the daily newspaper.

B. Ethics of Journalism

Commenting on the role of a newspaper is to mention the responsibility of the press. The topic of ethics of journalism is the hardest linkage topic to avoid because the newspapers are businesses in the private sector that their works may impact the ethical society. The researchers do believed that following the ethic of journalism could possibly help to protect journalists can decide initially before offering any further.

Pisit Chawala (2004) [7] explains that ethics is a part of moral of this occupation. It allows members to create regulations to conduct voluntary cooperation to conduct their works under the rules that agreed by majority of people in the society. In other words, is the guiding line for the press act on what they should have done regarding to ethical not legal obligations. It means that if you exist to do that against ethic you will not be punished by the law. But as it was agreed by the majority of the people in the community or society, the ethic become the ideal of living together peacefully as the human being. Thus they are a thought that above the law. That is, if there is a breach of ethical obligations to contract with society. If the future, the practitioner cannot do what they had promised, they will be punished by the potential deterioration of society.

Supa Sirima (1987) [8] identified three major ethics, professional should be follow are First, the principle of " The real truth " (Objectivity) Many people in the society always have a high expectations that are completely non-biased news and even interpolates personal opinion or feelings like love , hate message into the news, are not allowed to put in the news . Second, the principle of honesty since it is too risky to fool the reader. And the third is the principle of a human decency. Since the ethics of journalism is intimately involved with the social conditions and business conditions which means that we cannot separate the social and business needs.

The committee of the national press council of Thailand agreed to enact regulations on the ethics of the profession newspaper on March 30, 2008. The constitution of national press council act 1997, the committee of the national press council of Thailand agreed to enact regulations on the ethics of the profession newspaper. Relying on article no. 5 (1) and article no. 14 (4) that including the Code of Ethics for members of the Press Council of Thailand and the Code of Ethnic and Guideline for Newspapers [9].

Article no. 5, the newspapers must present news taking into consideration the Benefit of the public, not of an individual.

Article no. 14, the newspapers must cover the name and position of the person giving the news a secret. If it has pledged to source the newspaper to cover the pseudonym or alias that will appear in the newspaper that a secret.

And the article no. 15: the newspapers must take into consideration the humanitarian Principle and the dignity of an individual person when he or she is being presented in photo or mentioned in news story.

In conclusion, the ethics of journalism is the profession that was constituted in writing formats. Including the moral rules of society agree and under the consciousness of individual journalists.

For ideas and concepts about the ethics of the newspaper press is the "heart" in the professional journalist. It represents the responsibility of the newspaper to society as a part of the social responsibility. By ideas of the journalism ethic was regarded as the foundation of the duty of media to be completely accurate and appropriate which the researcher has brought this concept to be a basic primary principle in evaluate the "Guidelines crimes in the news about women victims." to study whether there is a moral responsibility to women victims of violence or not.

C. Role of Newspapers

Wilbur Schramm claimed a newspaper as a type of media made by skilled human to serve the needs of society. There are several important functions that press needs to do. First to give information about the movements of the various events that takes place in society. Second, was the stage of public opinion. Controversial issues in the issues that affect people in society. Third, being a source of knowledge to the public. As a source of cognitive enhancement this brings their progress and society. The Forth one is providing entertainment for people to relax the mind, relieve stress and fun. And the last one, fifth, to provide business information that might be useful to the business and economics of the society.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Research Methodology of this research was divided into two sections; content analysis and in-depth interview. The First section, the population was determined as the Thai language daily newspaper in Thailand. The selections of large communal (Full size) or Broad Sheet sizes are sold throughout the country daily with more than five years publish experiences. The Purposive sampling was used to select the sample newspaper. The selections of populist types are including two brands of the newspaper; Thairath and Dailynews. And the selections of qualitative newspaper types are also include two brands of the newspaper; Matchon and Thaipost. Then a sample survey and select the crimes with women victims of violence from all the newspapers all four brands newspaper which published during the period of one year study period from 1st January 2009 to 31st December 2009, a total of 184 pieces of crime news. The rotating sampling was used within the study by rotate every eight days. It is a result of circulating newspaper distributed daily, weekly and monthly distribution. The duration of the study period of eight days starting from the first week of January 2009, marked as the first week until the last week of December 2009, a total of 184 weeks as illustrated in details by the

following table.

TABLE I
 DATA OF NEWS COLLECTED FROM 184 WEEKS, FROM FOUR BRANDS DAILY NEWSPAPERS IN THAILAND

Month 2009	Sunday	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday
January	25				1	9	17
February		2	10	18	26		
March	22	30				6	14
April			7	15	23		
May	17	25				1	9
June			2	10	18	26	
July	12	20	28				4
August				5	13	21	29
September	6	14	22	30			
October					8	16	24
November	1	9	17	25			

Based on the consideration of the data selected, the study period are long enough to reflect the responsibility of presenting the crime news.

Forty-six Thairath newspapers presented about forty-nine news, twenty-eight photos of illustrations, forty-six head-line news and forty-six content news were referred women victims of violence within their publication.

Forty-six Dailynews newspapers reported about thirty-nine news, fourteen photos of illustrations, thirty-nine head-line news and thirty-nine content news were referred women victims of violence within their publication.

Forty-six Matichon newspapers reported about four news, none of photos of illustrations, four head-line news and four content news were referred women victims of violence within their publication.

Forty-six Thai Post newspapers have none of illustration, none of news and none of headlines related to the cruel crimes or any crimes against the women on their first page

All samples were critical analyzed and recheck the quality the samples coding by three group of professionals; the researchers, the professional journalists who has more than three years related experiences, and the communications academics.

The samples of news, headline news, brief news and content news were critical analyzed and classified the contents into three main types; the illustration of the crime news with the women victim, the headline of the crime news with the women victim of the violence and the contextual crime news with the women victim of the violence.

The illustration of the crime news with the women victim presented on the front page of four brands Thai Language daily newspapers were selected purposively. Total of forty-two illustration were coded, used the coding sheet to rate whether the news were presented appropriately or inappropriately. For an analysis of crime news illustration with the women victims of violence are considered about the appropriation in presenting crime news via considering the responsibility of professional journalist based on the regulations the professional news reporter's ethic, 2008. In reporting any news, the reporter must be strictly protected to

human rights of children, women and the disability people and the news reporting to public must not offer pornographic images, horribly ugly or regardless of public sentimental picture. The term of appropriate in this point of consideration refers to the visual presentation of women victims of violence; do not abuse the dignity of the person in the news, as well as not to aggravate suffering or tragedy which happened to the victim. In addition, the news reported must not contain a shameful display of pornographic or shocking news or a regardless of their knowledge or public consciousness. Contradictory to the term of inappropriate refers the meaning of sending a bad affects to the dignity of the person from the news, while, passing on the aggravate suffering or tragedy, happened to the victim. In addition, the news reported might not contain a shameful display of pornographic, shocking news or a regardless of their knowledge or public consciousness.

The data of headline news written about the women victims of violence in this study, the researchers consider and separate it in two aspects; the context of the crime news and the language using in the headline. The contexts of the news must be meaningful, not too far from the facts in the news and reflects the main idea or the main content of news. The term of appropriate in this section is refers to those news filled with meaning, not too far from the facts in the news and reflects the main idea or the main content of news. Meanwhile, the term of inappropriate at this point refer to the news may careless, go too far from the facts in the news and cannot reflects the main idea or the main content of news. The language using in the headline means using a language power to stress on the powerful violence. The language used in the context of the news is refers to an alias calling system with the unfair negative meaning that might made the victims, especially the women victim to feel worst. The analysis of language presented in the headlines that promote violence within the news by setting the unpleasant alias used to refer to women who are victims of violent are appropriate or inappropriate. At this point, the term of appropriate refers the headlines with the respectful language, presented the news with the polite words and using general words to set the alias to call the

victim with no abused meaning hidden. While, the inappropriate term means using inappropriate language with strong words that refers to the victim in the headlines in order to promote the news via the violence without concerning to effects of setting the unpleasant alias that reflects negative to call the women victims in the news.

The contextual crime news with the women victim of the violence were first considered in the aspect that presenting the news of crime with cares and respect to the victim's dignity and human right. The professional journalism must provide the truth as the information with no abuse in anyway. The researchers use the number of the words to analyze the contextual crime news. First the contextual crime news will be critical consider in details of the victim presented on the news including any information that might allow the general public know who is the victim. Identifying details such the name, age, occupation, domicile, residence, place of work, education background and their family linkage information must be careful. Second, the contextual crime news with the women victim of the violence was considered to separate by the subjects of the news. The crime news of violence against women in any act of violence that results to the women victims who have physical suffering, sexual suffering or psychological suffering, as well as threatening to commit such violence or freedom arbitrarily were divided into a violence occurring in the family, a violence arising in general community and a violence caused by the neglect of the state.

The data analysis of crime news from four brands daily newspaper in Thailand used a descriptive statistics which gives the percentage of crimes committed any violence against the women victims.

Then the in-depth interviews were held with total 11 professional newspaper editors, including crime reporters and editors from four brands daily newspaper in Thailand with experience working in journalism and have direct experience with crime news and crime news with the violence against women victims. The purposive sampling was used to select newspaper professionals from Thairath, Dailynews, Matichon and Thailand Post newspaper, comprising a total of 11 persons.

The professionals from Thairath are including, Mr.Nipon Wongpaisan, the assistant director of crime news media who have been experience working in a position of assistant director for Thairath total of twenty-four years, Mr. Prasoth Nivaitthong, a crime reporters who has experience working as a crime reporter for Thairath for two years .

The professionals from Dailynews are including, Mr. Chaai Patakhamin, the editor of the Dailynews who has experience working in a position of editor of the Dailynews for 28 years, Mr. Theerachai Thongsane, the chief editor of crime news section, Dailynews who has experience working for Dailynews, for twenty-four years and Mr. Tiraphot Phornvissanukul, professional crime reporter who has been reporting crimes for five years.

The professionals from Mathichon are including, Mr. Parkpoom Pongunphai, the editors of Matichon newspaper

who has experience working as the editor for Matichon more than twenty-five years, Mr. Thevin Nagapaisua, the chief of justice and crimes section of Mathichon newspaper, who has experience working as the professional journalists for fourteen years, Mr. Chinnawat Paatayanon, a professional journalist working in the justice and crimes section with total three years direct experiences.

And the professionals from Thaipost are including, Mr. Chatchai Naamtapee, the editor Thailand Post newspaper who has experience working as the editor for Thaipost for thirteen years, as long as Mr. Khonson Glomsingh, the head of crime news reporter and Mr. Kasemh Wearnarm, the professional crime reporters of Thaipost newspaper.

IV. FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Quantitative reporting crimes with the violence against the women victims on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand found that the popular news paper have more regular presented the crimes news on their papers than the qualitative newspaper such Mathichon and Thaipost. Thairath has the highest number in presenting crimes with the violence against the woman on their first page, with the forty-nine crime news from forty-six editions studied. The ones presented one the first page of Dailynews and Mathichon are in the second and the third by descending order. Interestingly, from the overall of research, there is none of such violence against woman on the first page of the Thaipost.

In addition, the analysis of 92 crime news with the women victims demonstrates that Thairath has shown the illustration more than others, they seem to focus on visual presentation as well as news details; there are about 66.67 percent of the total crimes news found were present with the illustrations. While the Dailynews delivers the crime news with 33.33 percent of crime news were delivered with the illustrations. This result is corresponds with the in-depth interviews with professional practitioners, found that Thairath give priority to crime especially the ones with the violence against the women and the illustrations were used as an important tools in delivering the crime news according to the professionals believe that a photo are more meaningful that words. These illustrations along with the crime news have helped in terms of sales. A good illustration must be must be contain with good components and no retouching. To deliver the crimes news with the photos must be careful to protect the victims' human right by presenting it with censorings on the face of the victim or other risk information.

Reporting crime related to the violence against women on the front page of the daily newspaper in Thailand found that it can be divided into three parts, the illustrations, the headlines, and the content news.

Fist the illustrations and the responsible on delivering the news with the photos, Thairath found to be lack of responsibility at this point, about 67.86 percentage of the crime news illustrations presented were identified as inappropriate pictures of the victims on the crime scenes. Less

than Thairath, Dailynews has more appropriate amount about 57.14 percentage of the crime news illustrations, mostly present with the black strip censoring on both the face of the victims and the offender who is one of her family.

The headlines about women who are victims of crime were studied in two aspects; the content of information and the language used in the headline. From the research found that Thairath, Dailynews and Thaipost have used the powerful language on the headlines as appropriate to the actual news in details presentation. This is demonstrated that the headlines of the daily newspapers in Thailand were presented under the actual information of the crime. But by analyzing the language used to set the alias to call the women victims found that Thairath call or refer to the victim with worst inappropriate words. The Daily News and Matichon have shown the more appropriate in using alias to nickname the women victims with the reasonable words.

The presentation in the details and the contents of the crime news, Thairath, Dailynews and Thaipost have appropriate delivered through this studied. Most newspapers featured a presentation on the ages of the victim, since the age of the victim affects the presentation of crime news on women victims regarding to the law that fully protect children, age younger than 18 years old. The professional must carefully present the news with the appropriate communication paths with proper protecting solutions.

The professional journalist operations of the newspaper, the researchers would like to states that from this studies of four brands Thai daily newspaper have a policy of not disclosing the real name of the victim. The policy detailed presentation of news varies depending on the policy and judgment of reporter team in each company including in the way of writing and the use of language in different journalistic level of each firm.

The illustration on the news provided on the quantitative newspapers, Thairath and Daily News have almost the same strategy to deliver news through the visual presentation, although the contents and details in reporting were done differently. In the case of raping case, Thairath has delivered the news with facial censored photos along with the details of the crimes, while, Dailynews delivered this crimes via the text description without photo of illustration.

From the studies of four brands daily newspaper in Thailand found that the contents written in the crime news always disclose the personal information of the victims while open more in the conditions surrounded such as the time and the environmental conditions of the event.

By considering on the ethics of the professional journalist, the presentation on the illustrations, the headlines and the contents and details of the crime news were delivered differently from different firm. Since the different organizations have their own strategy. Thaipost and Mathichon have the similar policies related to the crimes presentation that the paper will not publish any illustration of the victim. On the other hand, Thairath claims the rights and the duties of the professional journalist to publish the truth to

the general public without bias and the dailynews remain to be neutrality in delivery the crimes news.

Recommendations on the further study shall be focus on the perspectives from different positions of professionals such as the editors, the writer, the board of the directors and the photographers for example. And it might be interesting to many audients to study the relationship of the firms' policy and the perspectives of the professionals in presenting the crimes with the violence against the women.

From the results of this research all the stakeholder within the industry ,the ethics of the professional journalist may need to be trained and revised seriously in order to deliver the juristic and crime news properly without abusing on any dignity or human right especially to the victim of special groups such children, woman and disability for example.

As this study may claim to the professional journalist organization, the researchers do expect to see the power of controlling and protecting the victim of the crimes presented on the papers as it they have faced many sadness and tragic of life they suppose not to be affected by any news publishing. Beside the seminar among the professionals should be held occasionally to discuss and exchange opinions related to the professionalism as well as to find the proper solutions of further presenting the crimes to the general public.

And regarding to the research granted by the educational institution, the researchers would like to underline the necessary of the learning and practicing on the professional news reporter both in order to produce the graduates to meet the industry needs and also to integrate knowledge in practice of professional journalist.

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Supaporn Wimonchailerk was born in 1st January 1982 in Phayao, Thailand. She accomplished a bachelor of Art (Communication Arts) from Bangkok University, Thailand in 2004. Then in 2010, she completed her master of Art (Mass Communication Administration) from Thammasat University, Bangkok Thailand. Currently, Supaporn is working as a full-time lecturer in Film, Communication Arts for The Faculty of Management, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok Thailand.